

National Open Access Monitor Advisory Group Meeting, 24th September 2025,
14:30

Minutes

Aaron welcomed and congratulated his new full-time role of National Open Access Monitoring Officer

1. Minutes Approved for meeting on 10th February 2025: [Monitor Advisory Group Meeting 10 Feb.2025 minutes](#)
2. Funding and extension of National Open Access Monitor
 - a. Susan informed the group that funding from the HEA has been approved for 2026
 - i. The funder wants to see new developments and for the Monitor to evolve into an Open Research Monitor
 - b. Susan also informed the group that NORF is being wound down
 - i. It is no longer being hosted by the RIA, it will no longer be staffed from 2026, current projects will be funded into 2026
 - c. Susan has spoken to the HEA and is encouraging them to use the Monitor for reporting
3. Development – Group to discuss future development and priorities for the Monitor
 - a. Aaron updated the group on recent development work by OpenAIRE
 - i. Improvements (backend) regarding optimisation
 1. refinement on the calculations and generations of the charts
 2. regular updates of the RPOs after the updates of the OpenAIRE Graph
 3. improvements on the documentation (methodology and terminology)
 - ii. Added functionality
 1. “Link Results”, which enables primary dashboard managers to associate research outputs with their institution
 - a. claim affiliation via DOIs
 2. Implementation of a custom filtering mechanism
 - a. Introduced allow for the removal of erroneous attributions
 - iii. Licences Disambiguation in the OpenAIRE Graph
 - b. The group discussed how the National Open Access Monitor can be improved and developed. Considering how to expand the services provided by the Monitor
 - i. The group grappled with what an Open Science/Research Monitor might do

1. Could it monitor FAIR publications – FAIR measurements could be very useful. Possibly we could focus on the FAIR Data elements in the EOSC Observatory
 2. Could it provide data on publication impact and the impact of Open Science
 - a. Show impact and alignment with collaborative
 3. Can we display further information on collaborations
 4. Open Software is an interesting area to explore
 5. [Research Classification Ireland](#) – the monitor could report on these classifications
 6. **Action:** Jenny O’Neill will report to the group [DARIAH](#) the pan-European Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (the Irish node is hosted by TCD)
 7. The group agreed that OSMI Principles of Open Science Monitoring are a useful benchmark for our Monitor
 - a. **ACTION:** Aaron to create a framework with the OSMI Principles and get members to review and compare with the National Open Access Monitor
 8. Eddie – There are lots of tools that do bits of things. But it would be very useful to be able to demonstrate the benefits of supporting Open Science
4. Engagement and promotion of National Open Access Monitor
- Case Studies reviewing institutional data for CONUL Workshop in May (MU, Research Ireland, UG)
 - Institutional data reviews have proven very successful and are being rolled out with other institutions including, RCSI, UL and TCD
 - NORFest 2025- "*The Next Phase of Open Research Monitoring in Ireland: Community Priorities and Practice*"
 - IReL/OpenAIRE workshop asking to community to help shape the next phase of Open Research Monitoring has been accepted for NORFest 2025. This workshop will focus on open research monitoring in Ireland: what we track, why we track it, and how we can make these efforts more relevant and inclusive
 - [ARION](#)- Advancing Research Assessment through Integrated Open Practices and Narratives (HORIZON-WIDERA-2025 funding)
 - OpenAIRE submitted this proposal last week, and IReL have agreed to organise pilot studies for this project if it successful.

5. A.O.B.

6. Next meeting

- Group agreed to meet again following the NORFest discussion. OpenAIRE will present findings from the session, and we will workshop the next phase of the Monitor.
- We may look at expanding the membership and knowledge base of this Advisory Group at this point.
- Date to be confirmed

